

Lowering to the Occasion: Meeting Society's Energetic Charged Particle Needs in the Age of Proliferated LEO

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T. P. O'Brien
Space Sciences Department
Space Science Applications Laboratory

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Senior Vice President, Civil Systems Group

Authorized by: Civil Systems Group

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Abstract

The age of “proliferated LEO” is upon us, in which low Earth orbit (LEO) has far more satellites than geostationary orbit (GEO). Until recently, with about 450 active vehicles, GEO was king, but today, individual LEO constellations reach into the hundreds and thousands of vehicles. There are even plans for constellations in the tens of thousands. The space weather research and operations communities have developed over decades with a primary focus on geostationary and high-altitude energetic charged particle environments. Proliferated LEO challenges that emphasis and requires adaptation of the existing approaches to meet the evolving needs of a society that is changing how and, more importantly, where it uses space. In this report, we explore the unique needs of proliferated LEO systems and how they can be met with modest, but necessary, adaptations of the current research and operational infrastructure. We specifically recommend greater attention be given to realtime monitoring of geomagnetic cutoffs for solar particle access to the magnetosphere, inclusion of quasi-trapped electrons and the inner belt in radiation belt models, and field-aligned currents or other indicators and models of low-altitude surface charging be specified at low Earth orbital altitudes. Development of such tools builds primarily on existing research results and space assets, while further research promises to offer even greater improvement on forensic, specification, and forecast capability.

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1. Introduction: The Proliferation of Satellites in Low Earth Orbit

Until recently, geostationary orbit (GEO) was the most widely used orbit, with about 450 active satellites. Much about how we address energetic charged particle hazards to satellites has been built around this reality. It colors our space weather research, our observations, and our operations. For example, the only orbit for which NOAA's satellite hazard dashboard provides localized hazard indicators is GEO (<https://www.swpc.noaa.gov/communities/satellites>). Low Earth orbit (LEO) and several medium orbits have also been used, but none compared to GEO until recently. We are now in an age of proliferated LEO (pLEO), when individual LEO constellations alone count more vehicles than all of GEO.

The overtake of GEO began in 1997, when the first Iridium satellite was launched in what would become a constellation of 66 vehicles providing global phone coverage from LEO. At the time, this was a large constellation. For the next 20 years, constellations of dozens of vehicles were as large as any one mission would require. In 2018, plans for far larger LEO constellations began to be realized with the launch of the first Starlink satellite. The Starlink constellation now includes over 1,000 LEO satellites providing global internet service, and it is still growing. Other proposed constellations are of similar size, thousands of vehicles, and some proposals extend to sizes of tens of thousands of vehicles.

Figure 1 shows several current LEO missions along with planned and withdrawn pLEO constellations. One of the ways that the public finds out about pLEO constellations is when a company files a request for radio frequency license from the Federal Communications Commission (FCC) or similar regulatory body; hence, FCC filings become a valuable resource for tracking planned pLEO missions. As the figure shows, altitudes for these very large constellations range from 300 km to 1,500 km, with most being at the lower end of that range for disposal purposes. After the size and location of the pLEO constellations, the size and longevity of the vehicles themselves mark the next major departure from conventional satellites. Unlike GEO satellites and conventional LEO satellites, many of these pLEO satellites are small, necessarily low cost, and built to last only a few years.

Based on public statements made by the pLEO satellite manufacturers at conferences, we know that most of them have put greater emphasis on test flights for finding and fixing space environment vulnerabilities than have conventional satellites. This approach is generally impractical for the much more expensive, much more massive conventional vehicles. However, a test flight that lasts only a year or two will not expose the vehicle to the extremes of space weather. Most concerning is the impact of an extreme solar energetic particle (SEP) event—it is quite possible to fly a test for several years without experiencing a significant, much less an extreme, SEP event. SEP events have always been an important part of space weather monitoring and forecasting. However, unlike GEO vehicles, a LEO vehicle's exposure to SEPs is heavily modulated by its orbital position. Description of SEP access to LEO vehicle orbit is not presently provided by forensic or realtime space weather models and services. We will return to this issue later in this report.

More generally, when diagnosing and correcting issues discovered during a test flight, it is necessary to understand the environment in which the spacecraft was operating at the critical time. Therefore, monitoring and forensic reconstruction of the environment in LEO, which is quite different from the environment at GEO and other high altitudes, is necessary for understanding test flight data and for diagnosing any kinds of anomalies that occur during pLEO operations. Adding specification of conditions in LEO to our space weather monitoring, forecasting, and forensic capabilities will be the topic of the remainder of this report. First we will review the energetic charged particle hazards to spacecraft, and then we will examine internal charging, surface charging, and single-event effects hazards and their associated LEO charged particle environments, and how space weather research and operations need to change to address them in the dawning era of pLEO.

Figure 1. Current, planned, and withdrawn LEO constellations.
 (Figure courtesy of Ted Meulhaupt, data from FCC filings and press releases.)

2. Energetic Charged Particle Hazards to Satellites

There are four main space weather hazards to satellites posed by energetic charged particles: event total dose, single-event effects, internal charging, and surface charging. These four hazards are depicted in Figure 2. Figure 2a shows a meridional view of the nominal configuration of the radiation belts, with the color scale depicting dose in silicon behind 82.5 mils of aluminum. The radiation environment is typically divided into an inner belt and an outer belt with a low-radiation slot between them. Overlapping with and beyond the outer belt is the plasma sheet. Figure 2d includes both a radial coordinate (L) and a latitude coordinate that can be used depending on whether one is at high altitude or low altitude. These coordinates, like the plasma and radiation, are connected by magnetic field lines.

The inner belt is dominated by energetic protons (MeV to GeV), and it extends to low altitudes along magnetic field lines to manifest as the South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA), as seen in Figure 2e. The SAA is localized in LEO due to the offset of Earth's dipole-like magnetic field from the gravitational center of Earth. The outer belt is dominated by energetic (\sim MeV) electrons, and it also maps to low altitudes along the magnetic field, producing bands of radiation at high and low altitudes, overlapping with the equatorward edge of the auroral regions. The inner belt is very stable, while the outer belt and slot intensities fluctuate by orders of magnitude with geomagnetic activity. The slot region is not actually a specific location, as the local minimum in radiation depends on which radiation is being considered.

The plasma sheet is highly dynamic, being made up of lower energy (keV) particles that respond to a greater variety of forces and types of magnetic activity. The plasma sheet extends to low altitude along magnetic field lines and forms the aurora, including the field-aligned current systems depicted in Figure 2f.

Not shown in Figure 2 are SEPs. Episodically, the Sun will emit a coronal mass ejection (CME) that will flood interplanetary and near-Earth space with these particles. SEP access to near-Earth space is modulated by Earth's magnetic field, with access to regions deeper in the dipole-like field requiring higher energy for particles carrying a given amount of electrical charge.

All the particle populations described above are organized by Earth's magnetic field; therefore, so are the energetic charged particle hazards to satellites. Event total dose manifests mainly when SEPs produce enhanced dose over a few days on a satellite or subsystem unaccustomed to regular intense radiation dose. The prime example of this is solar cell degradation on geostationary satellites. Since GEO sits at the outer edge of the radiation belts, the primary radiation damage to GEO solar arrays arises from SEP protons. SEP protons are not present on the vast majority of days, which are quiet, but only appear episodically during SEP events. In other orbits, the dynamic outer belt or transient proton belts in the slot region might present an event total dose hazard. However, for LEO, there is effectively no (natural) transient dose source that can compete with the routine daily dose caused by the SAA, meaning LEO vehicles do not need to consider event total dose as a potential source of anomalies from the dynamic space weather environment.

Single event effects (SEEs) are caused by energetic protons of the inner belt, SEPs, and ever-present, cosmic rays that vary gradually on solar-cycle timescales. Many vehicles experience SEEs in the inner belt or SAA. Figure 2b shows single event upsets (SEUs) on the CRRES spacecraft. During SEP events, additional energetic particles are encountered at high altitudes and high latitudes. A parameter called the geomagnetic cutoff controls how deep into the magnetic field the SEPs reach in latitude or L , and therefore knowledge of this cutoff is important for understanding whether a given vehicle is exposed to an elevated SEE risk from SEPs during an SEP event. GEO, however, unlike almost every other orbit used by humanity, is entirely outside the cutoff. We will return to the topic of cutoffs in section 5.

Internal charging is caused by buildup over time of energetic electrons in materials and on surfaces interior to a spacecraft. It is caused mainly by outer radiation belt electrons, but inner belt electrons also contribute. Because it takes time for charge to build up and then discharge, leading to anomalies, the anomaly location does not precisely correlate with the location of the energetic electrons. Figure 2c shows the location of vehicle time code word (VTCW) anomalies on the CRRES spacecraft. These are most common in the outer belt but occur anywhere in the CRRES orbit due to the time delays. Figure 2e shows how the outer belt appears as two horizontal bands at subauroral latitudes in LEO, with the most intense region being just southeast of the SAA. The intensity and longitude structure of the low-altitude outer belt is highly dynamic, and we will return to it in section 3.

The final hazard in Figure 2 is surface charging. At high altitudes, it is caused by hot plasma sheet electrons, which are present mainly at local times before midnight through pre-noon. These electrons are injected or convected Earthward from the nightside tail of the magnetosphere into the region near geostationary orbit and convect east toward dawn local times under electric and magnetic forces. Plasma instabilities cool and disperse the plasma. Thus, most charging is observed in the pre-midnight to post-dawn sector on high-altitude vehicles. At low altitudes, some vehicles exhibit this same local time and L or latitude charging pattern associated with the diffuse aurora, which is broadly associated with plasma sheet particles, predominantly electrons, that are scattered by the magnetospheric waves and precipitated into the atmosphere. However, other vehicles exhibit surface charging only associated with discrete auroral arcs, which are associated with precipitating electrons from the plasma sheet that have been accelerated by electric fields parallel to the magnetic field lines, and that type of charging has its own local time pattern. Both types of auroral charging have been correlated with field-aligned currents, which are shown in Figure 2f. Field-aligned currents are broadly indicative of strong convection and typically also indicate the presence of hot (keV) plasma. We will return to these topics in section 4.

For proliferated LEO vehicles, like all LEO vehicles, only three of the four main space weather charged particle hazards apply: SEEs, internal charging, and surface charging. LEO vehicles experience charged particle hazards differently than high-altitude vehicles, and the LEO environment is far more structured and complex than the environment at geostationary orbit. A high-inclination LEO vehicle is likely to encounter every major particle population and associated hazard, and the details of those encounters will be modulated not just by Earth's magnetic field but also by how that field is offset from the neutral atmosphere. As such, LEO is a complicated place, requiring some special modeling efforts compared to the high-altitude radiation and plasma environment. Fortunately, driven by their curiosity and by the needs of other societal users, scientists have a ready arsenal of physics knowledge, observations, and research models that can be brought to bear to address the charged particle hazards faced by pLEO satellites.

Figure 2. Space weather energetic charged particle hazards to spacecraft: (a) a meridional view of total dose, (b) SEEs on CRRES, (c) internal charging on CRRES, (d) surface charging on SAMPEX, (e) contours of dose rate in LEO as well as ground tracks of a polar LEO vehicle, and (f) field-aligned currents in the northern polar region courtesy of B. Anderson, Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Lab.

3. Global Models Are Not Global: Missing Electron Populations and Internal Charging

The first charged particle hazard we examine for pLEO vehicles is internal charging, caused by inner and outer belt electrons. For high-altitude vehicles, internal charging is essentially only caused by the outer belt because high-altitude vehicles fly almost exclusively in the outer belt. Conversely, as shown in Figure 3, a LEO vehicle might never encounter the outer belt at all, depending on its altitude and inclination. Low-inclination LEO vehicles will only encounter the inner belt and slot region. Many “global” electron radiation belt models do not include the inner belt, and some do not include the slot. Figure 3 also shows how LEO inverts the geometric scale of the belts relative to high altitudes: the outer belt is very large at high altitude but very small in LEO, and the inner belt is small at high altitude and large at low.

Further, when higher-inclination LEO vehicles do encounter the outer belt, most of what they encounter is not stably trapped; it is, instead, quasi-trapped or drift loss cone (DLC) electrons. These are electrons that have been scattered by plasma waves so that their north-south bounce motion carries them to low-enough altitudes that they will strike the atmosphere before completing a full drift around Earth. A drift takes on the order of 15 minutes for electrons that cause internal charging, and so it is of little physical consequence to global radiation belt models to treat these quasi-trapped particles as not immediately lost. However, for LEO vehicles, these particles cannot be ignored when considering their internal charging hazard.

How can the scientific community address these missing pieces in LEO? First, global radiation belt models can add the inner belt. It is not a very dynamic environment, and so persistence models will probably work quite well using available observations from current NOAA/EUMETSAT SEM-2 observations and their follow-ons in LEO as constraints.

The DLC presents a more complicated challenge. However, there are unexploited observational and simulation capabilities that can be brought to bear. A series of papers by Selesnick and Tu [16][17][18] employ a drift-diffusion model to describe energetic electrons in the DLC. This model can be fit observationally at a one-day cadence with a single LEO satellite in polar orbit to specify the entire DLC, or it can be fit at higher cadence with more vehicles. The SEM-2 fleet currently contains five vehicles, allowing the DLC to be specified roughly every five hours. While another fleet, REACH [9][6], consisting of dozens of dosimeters, could be used to push the time resolution to approximately hourly updates. Using these purely empirical approaches, not only could the DLC itself be specified, a detailed description of radiation belt losses could be provided to global simulation models. Further, the Selesnick-Tu simulation could be added to global radiation belt simulations essentially as a post-processing step—there is no feedback from the DLC back into the trapped radiation belt simulation, and the trapped domain simulation already provides all the parameters needed by the DLC simulation.

Figure 3. High altitude (left) and low altitude (right) views of the radiation belts.

4. Surface Charging at Low Altitudes: Unknowns and Opportunities

The next charged particle hazard we consider for LEO vehicles is surface charging. Surface charging is caused by hot electrons in the plasma sheet at high altitude, which manifest at low altitude as both discrete auroral features (arcs) and the diffuse aurora. Operational auroral models tend to be focused on auroral impacts to the ionosphere and neutral atmosphere for impacts like satellite drag, radar clutter, radio propagation, scintillation, and impacts to satellite navigation. As such, the auroral parameters tend to be projected onto topside or bottomside ionospheric reference altitudes, well below most LEO vehicles. When considering how to address surface charging for pLEO, we are confronted with the usual specification problem, but we also face some uncertainty in just how the surface charging hazard actually manifests for a LEO vehicle.

There are three main surface charging datasets in LEO: DMSP [1], Freja [3] and SAMPEX [10]. The DMSP and Freja datasets both describe charging of the spacecraft frame relative to the ambient plasma. Based on these datasets, we know that frame charging occurs during conditions of low ambient plasma density and eclipse in the presence of hot electrons. Auroral arcs provide the necessary plasma conditions: electric fields parallel to the magnetic field lines evacuate the ambient cold plasma while accelerating other particles to high enough energies to produce a hot plasma capable of charging the vehicle relative to the nearby cold plasma. As such, the arcs also carry field-aligned electric currents (FACs). In O'Brien et al. [12], we found that DMSP charging events were more common in the presence of elevated FACs observed by the Iridium satellite constellation via the AMPERE project (ampere.jhuapl.edu). Neither DMSP nor Freja experienced anomalies during their frame-charging events, and this is also observed on high-altitude vehicles: frame charging itself is indicative of surface-charging risk but is not, by itself, hazardous. Thus, the discrete aurora and frame charging tell only part of the story of surface charging in LEO.

The SAMPEX data follow a different pattern entirely from the frame-charging examples. Mazur et al. [10] studied high-voltage anomalies on SAMPEX that showed a pattern consistent with precipitating particles from the plasma sheet. SAMPEX charging has the same spatial and activity dependence as high-altitude charging. This pattern is suggestive of the diffuse aurora, which blankets large swaths of LEO in hot plasma but does not simultaneously evacuate the cold plasma. In order to produce anomalies, it was hypothesized that the SAMPEX surface that charged was on the anti-sunward side of the vehicle and in its wake. In LEO, wake effects produce a very hard vacuum, making it unnecessary for there to be a natural void of cold plasma during a charging anomaly. The SAMPEX anomalies are likely differential charging: one surface of the vehicle is at a different electrostatic potential from others nearby, and a discharge between them upsets the operation of the vehicle. Differential charging is far more hazardous than frame charging. Our initial studies correlating SAMPEX surface-charging anomalies with AMPERE field-aligned currents have also shown good correlation, but correlations improved if we used a maximum current intensity over a several-minute time window. This suggests that either the AMPERE FAC maps are not precisely locating the FACs at the time of the SAMPEX anomalies, or that FAC activity is correlated with but not causative of the SAMPEX surface charging.

These initial studies with the SAMPEX charging anomaly data suggest a variety of ways to improve representation of the surface-charging hazard in LEO. Perhaps other parameters besides the FAC intensity correlate better with the SAMPEX anomalies and thereby the general charging risk. For example, ultraviolet (UV) imagers such as those flown in LEO on the DMSP (SSUSI) and TIMED (GUVI) satellites can be used to compute the total energy flux into the aurora and the mean energy of precipitating electrons in the $\sim 1\text{--}20$ keV range, with best sensitivity in the 1–5 keV range. The Polar spacecraft at high altitude carried a UV imager able to provide those same parameters in a global image, and it also carried an x-ray imager (PIXIE) was sensitive at the higher-energy (10s keV) range. Correlating these imager

datasets with the SAMPEX anomalies may reveal promising ways to monitor the LEO charging environment.

Auroral models also offer ways to monitor and forecast the LEO charging environment. For example, the empirical operational OVATION [11] energy-flux model can already be used to estimate where the diffuse aurora is and the probability of discrete aurora, as seen in Figure 4. It simply needs to be extended to enable one to map its parameters to LEO vehicles. However, because of limitations of how well empirical models can represent rare and extreme conditions of active and storm times, physics-based models offer a worthwhile investment. Global MHD numerical simulation models specify the location and intensity of FACs but do not presently specify their intensity at LEO altitudes. It is a straightforward application of physical conservation laws to map their FACs to LEO altitudes, but they lack important physics of magnetosphere-ionosphere (MI) coupling that is doubtless important to specifying the LEO surface-charging environment. There is a variety of numerical simulation models dedicated to more realistic representations of MI coupling (e.g., the Rice Convection Model – Equilibritum [2] and the SuperThermal Electron Transport, STET code [7][8]) that could be adapted to an operational auroral model for LEO surface charging. With the growth in utilization of LEO, it is time for a roadmap to develop an operational model for that purpose.

Figure 4. NOAA SWPC’s operational OVATION product shows energy deposition into the polar region but could potentially be used to indicate spacecraft surface-charging hazard if mapped to LEO vehicle locations.
<https://www.swpc.noaa.gov/products/aurora-30-minute-forecast>.

5. SEEs, SEPs, and Geomagnetic Cutoffs

The final hazard we will explore for pLEO is SEEs, caused by the protons in the SAA and by SEPs. Figure 5 shows how these particles are seen by the AeroCube-6 (AC6) vehicle [13][14] at ~650 km altitude. The Dos3 dosimeter on AC6-B responds only to >11 MeV protons. On a quiet day, the polar regions see a very low rate of cosmic rays as well as the very stable SAA. However, during an SEP event, the energetic particles flood the polar regions and extend equatorward up to the geomagnetic cutoffs. Poleward of the cutoff, the radiation environment is essentially the same as that at geostationary orbit, where it is monitored by NOAA's GOES spacecraft. (Transient proton belts sometimes slightly enlarge the SAA into the slot, but that hazard is partially addressed by existing NOAA belt index products.)

The cutoffs depend on the energy and charge state of the particles and vary over the course of the event as Earth's magnetic field is altered by geomagnetic activity. O'Brien et al. [15] showed that accurate specification of the cutoffs requires realtime monitoring. A single LEO satellite in a high-inclination orbit encounters the cutoff four times per orbit, or about every 25 minutes. However, there is presently no system in place to use any of our LEO assets to monitor and publish the cutoff in realtime or to use knowledge of the cutoff at one vehicle to estimate SEP fluxes throughout LEO or the rest of near-Earth space. NASA is currently funding development of the Solar Particle Access Model (SPAM) [4][5] to exploit the SEM-2 data available from POES and MetOp in near realtime. Implementing SPAM is the first step toward providing SEE hazard awareness to pLEO users. The REACH mission consists of 32 dosimeter pods hosted on the IridiumNEXT satellite phone constellation, enabling realtime downlink. A system based on REACH would improve upon the SEM-2-based monitoring system because it would have lower downlink latency, and it would directly measure any local time or longitude features rather than having to model them.

Figure 5. Count rates in the Dos3 dosimeter along the AC6-B ground track on (left) a quiet day and (right) a solar particle event day. The equatorward extent of solar particle access is controlled by geomagnetic cutoffs that vary with geomagnetic activity over the course of the event.

6. Summary and Recommendations

A new era of proliferated LEO has begun. Scientific concepts, research, and instrumentation that were explored mainly on the broad frontier of human curiosity are now summoned to transition into applications to address society's changing needs. Proliferated LEO missions have been using and will continue to use test flights, raising the stakes for what would already be an important problem of specifying the LEO environment for anomaly forensics for thousands of operational vehicles. The tools we have developed for high-altitude operations, especially geostationary orbit, will not suffice. While some of the forecasts and simulations we have developed for high-altitude operations address some aspects of LEO, the spatial structures in LEO are unique, and there are particle populations in LEO that are generally omitted from high-altitude models. Further, the use of test flights may expose some pLEO missions to unexpected vulnerabilities to extreme space weather, especially large solar energetic particle events, that are not always present in a ~1 year on-orbit test.

To specify the LEO environment for satellite operations and anomaly resolution, our tools and models need to address three main hazards: internal charging, surface charging, and SEEs. To address internal charging, the models must specify not only the outer belt electrons, which are their current focus, but they must also specify the inner belt and quasi-trapped DLC. Adding these should be a straightforward application of published methods using data from sensors already on orbit.

To address the surface-charging hazard, we will need a better understanding of how surface charging in LEO differs from high-altitude surface charging. Still, we know enough now to recognize that we must specify auroral parameters, such as field-aligned current intensity, at LEO altitudes. We must further investigate what other auroral parameters might also be correlated with LEO surface charging and incorporate that knowledge into further improving our surface-charging specification at LEO altitude. We should also produce a roadmap for development of an operational surface-charging model for LEO to guide the research-to-operations effort.

Finally, to address the SEEs hazard, we must monitor, in realtime, the geomagnetic cutoffs that control SEP access to LEO (and medium Earth orbit). This can be done with tens of minutes latency with the NOAA-MetOp constellation using a tool under development on NASA funding, and it could likely be done even better using the REACH data.

Development of existing scientific research into tools and technology can substantially meet the needs of the pLEO missions taking shape today. Further research will likely reveal opportunities to significantly improve forensic, specification, and forecast capabilities to serve the thousands of satellites that will be operating in the low Earth orbital environment.

7. Acronyms

AMPERE	Active Magnetosphere and Planetary Electrodynamics Response Experiment
CME	Coronal mass ejection
DLC	Drift loss cone, where quasi-trapped radiation belt particles reside before drifting into the SAA
CRRES	Combined radiation and release satellite
DMSP	Defense meteorological satellite program
EUMETSAT	European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites
FCC	Federal communications commission
GEO	Geostationary or geosynchronous orbit
GNSS	Global navigation satellite system
GOES	Geostationary operational environment satellite
GUVI	Global ultraviolet imager. UV imager on TIMED.
JHU APL	Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Lab
LEO	Low Earth orbit
LICA	Low energy ion composition analyzer, a particle detector on SAMPEX
MEP	Microelectronics package, a technology test package on CRRES
MI coupling	Magnetosphere-ionosphere coupling
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OVATION	Oval variation, assessment, tracking, intensity, and online nowcasting. Model of the aurora.
PIXIE	Polar ionospheric x-ray imager experiment. X-ray imager on Polar.
pLEO	Proliferated LEO (very large LEO constellations)
R_E	Earth radius = 6378 km
REACH	Responsive Environmental Assessment Commercially Hosted, dosimeters hosted on 32 IridiumNEXT satellites in LEO
SAA	South Atlantic Anomaly

SAMPEX	Solar, anomalous, and magnetospheric particle explorer
SEE	Single event effect
SEM-2	Space Environment Monitor 2, a radiation sensor suite hosted on LEO weather satellites
SEP	Solar energetic particle
SEU	Single event upset
SPAM	Solar particle access model
SSUSI	Special sensor ultraviolet spectrographic imager. UV imager on DMSP.
STET	Superthermal electron transport
SWPC	Space weather prediction center
TIMED	Thermosphere, ionosphere, mesosphere, energetics and dynamics satellite
VTCW	Vehicle time code word, a clock jump anomaly on CRRES

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Approved Electronically by:

Robert D. Rutledge, DIRECTOR - DEPARTMENT
SPACE SCIENCE APPLICATIONS LABORATORY
PHYSICAL SCIENCES LABORATORIES
ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY GROUP

Cognizant Program Manager Approval:

Joseph E. Mazur, PRINCIPAL DIRECTOR
PHYSICAL SCIENCES LABORATORIES
ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY GROUP

Aerospace Corporate Officer Approval:

Edward M. Swallow, SENIOR VP CIVIL SYSTEMS GROUP
OFFICE OF EVP

Content Concurrence Provided Electronically by:

T Paul P. O'Brien, SENIOR SCIENTIST
MAGNETOSPHERIC & HELIOSPHERIC SCIENCES
SPACE SCIENCES DEPARTMENT
ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY GROUP

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Office of General Counsel Approval Granted Electronically by:

Kien T. Le, ASSISTANT GENERAL COUNSEL
OFFICE OF THE GENERAL COUNSEL
OFFICE OF GENERAL COUNSEL & SECRETARY

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Angela M. Farmer, SECURITY SUPERVISOR
GOVERNMENT SECURITY
SECURITY OPERATIONS
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